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“A STUDY TO ASSESS DRUG UTILIZATION ON TYPE 2 D/M PATIENTS WITH OR WITHOUT COMPLICATIONS IN GENERAL WARD OF TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL AT VIJAYANAGAR INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES, BALLARI, KARNATAKA”

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ABSTRACT

A Prospective observational study was carried out for the period of six months in inpatient Department of General Medicine at Vijayanagar Institute of Medical Sciences, Ballari. Objective: To study the antidiabetic drug utilization pattern in hospitalized patient with type II diabetes mellitus with or without complications. Results: A total of 200 patients were chosen for the study, 54% of the patients were males and 46% of the patients were females. Most of the patients were in the age group of 51-65 years (49.5%). The major co morbidities identified were 76 patients (38%) with cardiac complications, followed by 41 (20.5%) patients had other concurrent illness & 25 (12.5%) had nephritic complications. Antidiabetic drugs accounted for 338 of the total drugs prescribed. Among the antidiabetic, Insulin was prescribed in 159 patients, accounted for 47.04%, followed by Biguanides (Metformin) were prescribed in 114 patients, accounted for 33.73%, Sulfonylureas were prescribed in 60 patients, accounted for 17.75%, α - Glucosidase Inhibitor were prescribed in 02 (0.591%) patients and Meglitinide were prescribed in 03 (0.888%) patients. Antibiotics were widely used 170 (25.56%) of all prescribed drugs (n=665) followed by PPI/H₂RA in 139 (20.90%) prescriptions. Conclusion: The prescribing pattern of drugs should be based on severity of disease condition, associated co morbid conditions and currently available evidences. The prescribing trend has been monotherapy with insulin followed by antidiabetic drugs in the form of Insulin and Metformin Combination.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by associated elevated blood glucose level resulting by defective mechanism of insulin action or its resistance or both [1]. However alter metabolism of carbohydrates, lipids and proteins with absence of insulin secretion result in diabetes.

Three main types of DM are: Type I DM insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) or "juvenile" diabetes is an autoimmune disorder where antibodies destroy β cells of islets of Langerhans it usually occurs in young children and adolescents, hence called juvenile onset diabetes mellitus.

Type II DM results from insulin resistance, a condition in which cells fail to use insulin properly, sometimes combined with an absolute insulin deficiency. (Formerly referred to as noninsulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) or "adult-onset" diabetes). Type II DM occurs of maturity onset when a diabetogenic lifestyle (excessive calories, inadequate exercise, and obesity) is superimposed upon a susceptible genotype most patients are obese and with reduce insulin sensitivity of tissues [5].

Gestational Diabetes when pregnant women, who have never had diabetes before, have a high blood glucose level during pregnancy. It may precede development of type II DM.

Uncommon causes of diabetes (1% to 2% of cases) include endocrine disorders like (acromegaly, Cushing's syndrome), gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), diseases of the exocrine pancreas (e.g. pancreatitis), and medications (e.g. glucocorticoids, pentamidine, niacin, and alpha interferon. Type II DM, once called non-insulin dependent diabetes, is the most common form of diabetes, affecting 90% to 95% of population which are chiefly associated with insulin resistance syndrome.³ Prolonged hyperglycemia results in various complications including premature atherosclerosis and retinopathy, nephropathy; gangrene of limbs. This is thought to be reduced blood supply to these structures because of thickening of capillary walls [4].

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic disorder emerging as major health problem; this increases the rate of morbidity and mortality. Diabetes is also a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease, stroke, and kidney failure. There has been worldwide increase in prevalence of DM, especially in developing countries. The prevalence of diabetes for all age groups worldwide was estimated to be 2.8% in 2000 and 4.4% in 2030. As per WHO, around 31.7 million individuals in India were affected by diabetes during the year 2000 which may further rise to 79.4 million by the year 2030. In India onset of diabetes is about a decade earlier than their western counterparts [17]. In India, the majority of patients with DM are in the age group of 45–64 years, whereas in the developed countries these are in the age group of >65 years. DM can cause both morbidity and mortality and requires appropriate treatment to improve the quality of life [18]. According to international diabetes federation an estimate of 382 million persons with diabetes in India in 2013. This may rise to 592 million by 2035 [1, 2].

Type II DM is associated with chronic complications that are subdivided into microvascular and macrovascular complications [4]. Cardiovascular disease (CVD), which is a common macrovascular complication, is a major cause of mortality and morbidity in Type II DM patients, representing approximately 50% of all fatalities. According to the World Heart Federation, people with diabetes are 2–4 times more likely to develop CVDs. Intensive glycemic control that targets a glycated hemoglobin (A1C) of 7% and below can help to prevent or slow the progression of microvascular complications such as diabetic retinopathy and chronic kidney disease (CKD) in Type II DM patients [27]. Accumulation of glycosylated products in vessel walls may be responsible for thickening of capillary walls moreover intra cellular glucose is converted into sorbitol by enzyme (aldose reductase).this sorbitol exerts osmotic effect resulting in tissue damage and particularly in retina and peripheral nerves. As such DM does not cause significant troublesome symptoms however it is necessary to maintain normal blood glucose level to avoid further diabetic complications [2].

Aims & Objectives

- The aim of the study is to determine the drug utilization pattern in hospitalized patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus with or without cardiac complications.
- To evaluate drug utilization pattern of anti-diabetic drugs.
- The current objective of study is to screen the prescription trends in type2 diabetes mellitus patients with or without cardiac complications.
- Assess glycemic control and cardiac parameters (if any) in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Materials & Methods

Study Site

The study conducted at General Medicine Department of VIMS, Ballari, Karnataka

Study Design

A prospective, Observational study

Sample Size

200 Patients

Study Duration

The study conducted for a period of six months

Study Criteria

The study was carried out by considering the following inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

1. Type 2 diabetes with or without complications.
2. Age >18years
3. Hospitalized for D/M and its complications like Macro vascular (Coronary artery disease, HTN, Peripheral vascular disease, Dyslipidemia.) and Micro vascular (Retinopathy, Neuropathy & nephropathy) conditions.
4. Patient those who have the history of D/M or recently diagnosed.

Exclusion criteria

1. Age below 18 years
2. Gestational diabetic patients
3. Juvenile D/M patients.

Source Of Data

Patient profile record and treatment chart.

Data collection form

A Suitably designed data collection form developed and it includes the information regarding Anti-Diabetic drugs and other drugs used to treat its co-morbidities.

Study Procedure

In this study, 200 cases were collected in which drugs were administered for type II diabetes mellitus as well as choice ascertained to concurrent illness. The patients were involved in the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. In this study, the types of ADDs mostly administered to patients in single, combination or in triple therapies were evaluated. The gender, age of the patient, type of ADDs, with or without concurrent illness with relevancy was studied. The medical history consisting of inpatient medical records were reviewed for specific period of time. Data recorded as patient's clinical status; drug's administered for type II DM and other type of complications.

Data collected from the enrolled subjects were assessed and analyzed with the help of Microsoft Excel. The results were tabulated and counted in numbers and percentage, followed by representing the data with the aid of bar and pie diagrams.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1: Gender Wise Distribution.

Figure 2: Patient Age Wise Distribution.

Figure 3: Age Wise Distribution in Percentage.

Figure 4: Distribution of Co morbidities.

Figure 5: Distribution of Co morbidities in Percentage.

Figure 6: Antidiabetic drugs utilization pattern.

Figure 7: Drug utilization pattern in Monotherapy.

Figure 8: Drug utilization pattern in Dual Therapy.

Figure 9: Drug utilization pattern in Triple Therapy.

Table 1: Overall usage of individual Antidiabetic drugs.

Name of The Class	Name of The Drug	Number of Patients	Percentage
Insulin	Insulin Regular	132	39.05%
	Insulin Mixtard	24	7.10%
	Insulin Actrapid	03	0.888%
Biguanide	Metformin	114	33.73%
	Sulphonylureas		
Sulphonylureas	Glimepiride	58	17.16%
	Glibenclamide	02	0.591%
α- Glucosidase I	Voglibose	02	0.591%
Meglitinide	Repaglinide	03	0.888%
	Total	n=338	100%

Figure 10: Utilization pattern of other drugs.

DISCUSSION

In this study a total of 166 (83%) patients suffers from certain specific co morbidities, out of 166 co morbid case cardiac complication accounted for 76 (38%), which is lower than the study done in Bangalore, Karnataka (Pavan Gara et al) [20] which was found to be 112 (66.27%) complications out of 169 complications. Similarly it was lower than the study done in Andhra Pradesh (Abbasi et al) [1] which was found to be 59.3% of total complications. The study conducted on western Odisha (Agrawal R et al) [14] reveals 39.1% of cardiac complication which is similar to our study. Antibiotics were the most frequently prescribed class of agents for concurrent illness may be to treat or prevent the underlying infections.

Increase in utilization of Insulin was recorded in majority of patients due to presence of co morbid conditions or resistance to oral hypoglycemic drugs. This justifies higher use of Insulin in hospitalized patients in present study. The rationale for using Insulin in combination with Metformin is that; combining Insulin with an agent that is known to sensitize the liver to the action of Insulin is at least additive or may be synergistic action in controlling blood sugar level [17]. The pattern of antidiabetic drug utilization most common therapy in which the antidiabetic drug prescribed was monotherapy (53.50%), followed by dual therapy (38%) and triple therapy (8.50%) which was found to be similar to the study conducted in western Odisha (Agrawal R et al) [14] and study conducted in Uttar Pradesh (Shahir Quazi A et al) [9]. Similarly the monotherapy was commonly prescribed (49.5%) in the study conducted at Bangalore, Karnataka (Pavan Gara et al) [20].

In monotherapy Insulin is most utilized drug in which Insulin Regular was most frequently used followed by Metformin and Glimepiride respectively. In contradiction to this study, the study conducted in Madhya Pradesh (Sharma P et al) [11] reported Metformin as the most commonly prescribed antidiabetic agent as monotherapy during hospital stay of the patient. Metformin is well established safe drug over the period of use. Metformin has many advantages like beneficial effect on cardiovascular risk factor and it doesn't promote weight gain. Metformin improves lipid profile, delay progression of diabetes and prevents microvascular as well as macrovascular complication. It reduces insulin resistance, is unlikely to induce hypoglycemia and may have a positive influence on pancreatic beta cell. It can be combined with any other oral or injectable antidiabetic as required [17, 18].

Being more potent and clinically superior than first generation, only second generation sulfonylurea are used that is, Glimepiride is most widely used sulfonylurea worldwide [7]. In present study it was noticed that Glimepiride was most commonly prescribed sulfonylurea, advantage of lower incidence of hypoglycemia might be the reason for recommendation of Glimepiride over other sulfonylureas.

Adding a second agent is usually better than increasing the dose of an agent that has already been prescribed in nearly maximum doses. In some patients three drug combinations may be useful [5]. Several study shows that a combination of sulfonylurea with biguanide has been most widely used. In the present study prescription of combination of Insulin + biguanide > biguanide + sulfonylurea > Insulin + sulfonylurea > meglitinide + sulfonylurea > meglitinide + biguanide found to be practiced. The result of various studies have shown that the combination of Insulin either with biguanide or with sulfonylurea is more effective than Insulin alone in treatment of patients with type 2 DM after secondary failure of monotherapy, leading to better control on glucose profile. The only prescribed three drug combination in the present study was Insulin + Metformin + Glimepiride. Similar results were obtained in the studies done by Dutta S et al, Mandal S et al and Patel B et al [7, 16]. The overall prescribing practice was found to be similar to various other studies conducted in other parts of India.

CONCLUSION

In our study, males were found to be more affected by type 2 diabetes mellitus than females. Prevalence of diabetes has been found higher in male as compared to female and majority of the patients having diabetes in the age group of 51-65 years. Among the various complications, cardiovascular complications caused major threat, of which hypertension was most common. In this study, the prescribing trends found to be monotherapy with insulin followed by oral antidiabetic agents because of presence of higher incidences of co-morbidities. Among oral antidiabetic agents, Metformin accounted as most commonly prescribed oral antidiabetic drug. In the sulphonylurea class Glimperide was mostly prescribed. Insulin along with Metformin was most commonly used combination followed by Metformin along with Glimperide combination. Overall, monotherapy was found to be predominant over combination therapy.

Along with the antidiabetic drugs other various classes of agents like Antibiotics, PPI/H₂RA, and Calcium channel blockers were commonly used to treat the concurrent illness.

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REFERENCES

1. Abbasi M.Y, Ali Md.A, Alshammari M. A prospective study on prescribing pattern of anti-diabetic drugs. World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences. 2014; 3(5): 45-47
2. Haghghatpanah M, Thunga G, Jha A, Mallayasamy S. Study on prescribing pattern of anti-diabetic drugs among type 2 diabetes patients with complications in south Indian teaching hospital. Asian journal of pharmaceutical and clinical research. 2016; 9(1): 194-197
3. Aiswarya P, Roshni PR. A study on prescribing practice and general trends of diabetes among patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital. International research journal of pharmacy. 2015; 6(8): 505-508
4. Kumar K.S, Sreerama G, Krishna K.M, Nalini K, Kiranmai N, Vasavi P. Drug use pattern of antidiabetics in type 2 diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care hospital in Tenali, Andhra Pradesh. International journal of inventions in pharmaceutical sciences. 2013; 1(3): 162-166
5. Kananan, Arshad, Kumar S. A study on drug utilization of oral hypoglycemic agents in type-2diabetic patients. Asian journal of pharmaceuticals and clinical research. 2011; 4(1): 60-64
6. Joshi H, Mary R, Padil G.M, Shastry C.S and Pathak. R. Investigation of in-patient prescribing patterns of oral antidiabetic drugs in a tertiary care teaching hospital. African journal of pharmacology and therapeutics. 2013; 2(2): 54-58
7. Dutta S, Beg M.A, Anjoom M, Varma A, Bawa S. Study of prescribing pattern in diabetes mellitus patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital at Dehradun,Uttarakhand. 2014; 3(11): 1351-1354
8. Ramesh R, Kumar S.V, Gopinath S, Gavaskar B and Gandhiji G. Diabetic knowledge of rural community and drug utilization pattern in a tertiary care hospital. International journal of pharmacy and life sciences. 2011; 2(1): 531-535
9. Shahir Quazi A, Kauser S, Dharmender G and Ahmad niaz A. Prescribing pattern of antidiabetic medications in a tertiary care hospital. Journal of pharmaceutical and scientific innovation. 2013; 2(1): 41-46
10. Mailti T, Chakravarthy S, Mandal S, Panda A, Gangopadhyay T, Dan S. A study on drug utilization pattern in patients of type II diabetes mellitus attending referral diabetic clinic at a tertiary care teaching hospital in rural Bengal. European journal of pharmaceutical and medical research. 2016; 3(9): 641-647
11. Sharma P, Sharma N, Parakh R, Sharma N, Gautam B, Motiwale S. Screening of prescriptions in patient of type-2 diabetes mellitus in a tertiary care teaching hospital. International journal of pharmaceutical research and bio-science. 2014; 3(1): 401-409
12. Pradeep P, Prudhvi Kumar M, Praveen P, Poornima Sravya M, Chandra Sai P, Vinod Kumar M, Ramya R. A prospective,Pharmacoepidemiologic study on assessment of Anti-Hyperglycemic drug prescription pattern. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research. 2015; 4(2): 74-83
13. Kasture P, Kasture S, Khade N and Adnaik R.S. A study on drug utilization pattern of anti-diabetic drugs in rural area of Islampur. Der pharmacia letter. 2015; 7(5): 33-37
14. Agrawal R, Rath B, Saha K, Mohapatra S. Drug utilization pattern of antidiabetic agents in a tertiary care hospital of western Odisha India. International journal of basic and clinical pharmacology. 2016; 5(5): 2222-2226
15. Shah S, Shelke S, Patil P.A and Mgdum CS. A study on drug utilization pattern of anti-diabetic drugs in rural areas of Islampur and Kasegaon at Maharashtra.International journal of research in pharmacy and chemistry. 2017; 7(1): 60-62
16. Sekhar Mandal, Maiti T, Asoke Kr. Das, Abhijit Das, Ananya Mandal, Biswanath Sharma Sarkar, Soumitra Manda. Drug utilization study in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus attending diabetes clinic of a tertiary care hospital in rural Bengal. International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology. 2016; 5(4): 1647-1654.
17. Dashputra AV, Badwaik RT, Borkar AS, Date AP, Kalnawar NR. Pattern of antidiabetic drugs in outpatient and hospitalized patients in a tertiary health institute of central India. 2014; 2(3): 48-54
18. Rani J, Reddy S. Prescribing pattern of anti diabetic drugs in urban population of Hyderabad. National journal of physiology, pharmacy and pharmacology. 2015; 5(1): 5-9

19. Das P, Das B.P, Rauniar G.P, Roy R.K and Sharma S.K. Drug utilization pattern and effectiveness analysis in diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care Centre in Eastern Nepal. *Indian Jphysiolpharmacol.* 2011; 55(3): 272-280
20. Pavan Gara, Md. Imran, George M. Varghese, Arun J, Basavaraj K.Nanjwade. A prospective study on prescribing pattern and drug-interactions in type 2 diabetes patients with comorbid cardio complications in a teaching hospital. *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences.* 2016; 5(5): 1115-1132
21. Ankam S, Aluri V, Marella A, Guttu P. Drug prescribing pattern and evaluation of hypoglycemic drugs in a tertiary care hospital. *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences.* 2015; 4(10): 1333-1346
22. Alex S.M, Sreelekshmi BS, Smitha S, Jiji KN, Menon A.S, Uma D.P. Drug utilization pattern of anti-diabetic drugs among diabetic outpatients in a tertiary care hospital. *Asian journal of pharmaceutical and clinical research.* 2015; 8(2): 144-146
23. Janagan T, Kavitha R, Sridevi S.A, Veerendra V. prescription pattern of anti hypertensive drugs used in hypertensive patients with associated type 2 diabetes mellitus in a tertiary care hospital. *International journal of pharmaresearch and review.* 2014; 3(1): 1-5
24. Sivashankari V, Manivannan E and Priyadarshini S.P. A prospective, observational study on drug utilization pattern of anti-diabetic drugs in a rural area of tamilnadu, south india. *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences.* 2013; 4(1): 514 – 519
25. Patel B, Oza B, Patel KP, Malhotra S.D, Patel V.J. Pattern of antidiabetic drugs use in type-2 daibetic patients in a medicine outpatient clinic of a tertiary care teaching hospital. *International journal of basic & clinical pharmacology.* 2013; 2(4): 485-491
26. Ashar S.M, Hanif A, Jadoon A, Rehman M, Ullah N, Kamal Z, Hussain H, Yasmeeen S. Assessment of drug use pattern using WHO prescribing indicators in the medication therapy of indoor diabetic patients. *International journal of basic medical science and pharmacy.* 2016; 6(1): 16-20
27. Huri H.Z, Ling DYH, Ahmad WAW. Association between glycemic control and antidiabetic drugs in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with cardiovascular complications. *Drug design, development and therapy.* 2015; 9: 4735-4749
28. Mary Lynn Davis-Ajami, Jun Wu, Jeffrey C.Fink. Differences in Health Services Utilization and Costs between Antihypertensive Medication Users Versus Nonusers in Adults with Diabetes and Concomitant Hypertension from Medical Expenditure Panel Survey Pooled Years 2006 to 2009 Value in health. 2014; 17(1): 51-61.

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